

Memories of San Antonio before the Great Hill Country Flood by Brian Paul Kaess

On the 2025 July 4th weekend, catastrophic flooding struck the Hill Country area north of San Antonio, Texas (especially Kerrville), and a wave of memories began flooding back to me from my previous stints as a soldier, student, & husband in the 'Alamo City.' The Hill Country was always fondly remembered by me as a place where only affluent Texans lived, including many Northwestern students in my UTSA German class, who were just there to pick up some summer credits, while jet-setting back-and-forth each semester from Illinois to their 'pasche' Hill Country homes. I also remember meeting an attractive, 'meaty' female Hispanic student at UTSA, who asked me inquisitively, 'What is your major?' At that time, I was pretty much undecided, but had just switched to History so as to major in 'something' and not be a dork. When I told her that, she replied softly: 'You don't look like a History Major.' She was becoming rather flirty, and I was starting to dig it, and if it wasn't for Ellen and the kids waiting at home, I would have been off to the races to her Saloon!

There was also the time I took my stepson Steven Ray Ellsberry to a pickup basketball game that almost turned violent. This took place at a public basketball court to seem to have an ok crowd, until I joined in. At this point, I had been practicing basketball a lot at a 'private court' at the 'old' Texas Military Institute (TMI), literally having the place to myself, since it was closed down and I was a security guard there. I had free run of the place, and I used my time when I wasn't studying to practice 'hoops.' If anything, it was good exercise.

So, when I started to mingle before this pickup game (with my stepson watching), one of the caucasian players told me he had just graduated from high school in San Antonio, and was headed on a basketball scholarship to Duke. But when the play started, perhaps to his dad's and his own disbelief, I managed to outclass him a little, knowing a few moves of my own from being a hard-core street court player in Chicago during my teens. Who knows, maybe I managed to best him a little because his obese dad seemed to start fuming, perhaps wondering how someone, who was just a 'townie,' was beating his kid!

After a few rounds of play, the mood became more heated, and I started receiving 'cheapshots' and flagrant ones at that. I just smiled and brushed it off, and eventually, just walked off the court, holding my stepson's hand, leaving as it were, as we were happy to avoid a 'fracas.' During that time period, we managed to see Michael Jordan and the Bulls play the Spurs in San Antonio, and I was happy to watch 'MJ' pour in 40 pts. during a losing effort.

Then I remember working on the Pediatric Ward at Brooke Army Medical Center as a Medic. One Hispanic NCO, who had lost his twin brother during the Vietnam War, asked me: 'Do you like kids?' and when I answered 'Yes,' he took me 'under his wing' and placed me on the Pediatric Ward. Of the many nice people I met there, I think I only remember three names: Sgt. Irizarry (LPN), Sharon (RN), and Capt. Rumm (MD). I must have been in a hurry to get out of the military. One older civilian nurse, noting my constant reading of an NEIU catalog, urged me 'to study hard' when I got to college.

I was often working extra shifts and things became even more hectic when they placed me in the Pediatric ICU, adjacent to the larger Pediatric Ward, to specifically take care of a terminal Asian-American kid who had brain cancer. I was doing vital signs Q2! I gave him OK care, but this didn't stop his decline and eventually he passed, much to my chagrin. His parents, a white, male GI, and Korean-looking mother, were able to see him and play with the 'child', and they all seemed to smile at each other a lot. I think they may have been brought from overseas to receive extra help stateside. But, dissapointingly, it was to no avail.

Because I worked many extra shifts, I was given an Army Achievement Medal, which may have been a 'carrot' to try and get me to reenlist. I did, but not in the active Army, but the Illinois Army National Guard, with the unit on Broadway Ave on the North Side.

When Ellen was busy, and I had some time off and wanted to do more than play 'Mr. Mom,' I took my stepdaughter Heather Marie Ellsberry (who I was babysitting) to the McNay Art Museum which had many Impressionist pieces, and a bright, sunny airy atmosphere. This was in stark contrast to a more avante-garde low-budget Art museum we saw that was displaying more controversial and politically-charged art. I am not even sure the latter place still exists. It was dark with black walls, and barely sufficient lighting, with one exhibit displaying a lone TV in the center of the room, broadcasting a political message, meant to be taken up or critiqued by the audience. In any case, Heather and I had fun 'zooming' around town in the Suzuki, and returned safely to our NE (?) side apartment.

I also spent time previously at Fort Sam Houston, Texas, for Advanced Individual Training (AIT) as a Combat Medic, and was able to see my Granduncle Francis Aubrey Swartz at his apartment at the Spanish Trace apartments, also on the NE side. When I later lived in San Antonio¹ offbase with Ellen, I was able to visit my Grandmother Margaret Jane (Swartz) Langley, and we would bring her canned food as a favor. Some dude offered me a job as a fork lift operator at a fertilizer warehouse, and the pay seemed good, but I would've 'taken my eyes off the prize' of a college degree. Ellen and I had some good times eating with the kids at local restaurants and going to bars such as TGIF's. In the long run, it didn't really work out between me and Ellen, but I can't say I don't have a fondness for San Antonio and the Hill Country.

Years later, Mayte and I stopped by an excellent Tex-Mex Buffet restaurant in San Marcos, Texas, also in the Hill Country, with plenty of dark-dressed, slinky-clad waitresses to boot, and an excellent menu. It was so hot getting off the bus in San Marcos, I thought I was going to pass out. But that's Texas for ya, a 'whole other Country!'

¹ I earned a Texas driver's license in 1989 or so, and was thus, briefly, a Texas resident. UTSA even let me slide on paying out-of--state tuition, perhaps because I was married to a serviceperson (i.e. Ellen).